

Advanced search

- Documents
- Authors
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Search tips ⓘ

Enter query string

TITLE-ABS-KEY((((step* OR stride*) W/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*)) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR "single support" OR "double support") W/2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*)) OR (((spatiotemporal OR "spatio-temporal") W/2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*)) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) W/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR rhythm* OR volume* OR bout* OR duration* OR distance* OR intensit* OR variabilit* OR asymmetr* OR symmetr* OR parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic* OR assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR measure* OR test*))))))

Outline query Add Author name / Affiliation Clear form Search Q

ALL("Cognitive architectures") AND AUTHOR-NAME(smith)
 TITLE-ABS-KEY(*somatic complaint wom?n) AND PUBYEAR AFT 1993
 SRCTITLE(*field ornith*) AND VOLUME(75) AND ISSUE(1) AND PAGES(53-66)

Operators

- AND +
- OR +
- AND NOT +
- PRE/ +
- W/ +

Field codes ⓘ

- Textual Content ▼
- Affiliations ▼
- Authors ▼
- Biological Entities ▼
- Chemical Entities ▼
- Conferences ▼
- Document ▼
- Editors ▼
- Funding ▼
- Keywords ▼
- Publication ▼
- References ▼
- Subject Areas ▼

Search history

Combine queries...

e.g. #1 AND NOT #3

- | | | | |
|---|---|--------------------------|--|
| 4 | (TITLE-ABS-KEY(((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) W/3 obstruct*) OR copd OR parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans" OR ((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) W/3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat* OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) W/5 fracture*)) AND.(View More ▼ | 8,755 document results | |
| 3 | (TITLE-ABS-KEY(((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) W/3 obstruct*) OR copd OR parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans" OR ((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) W/3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat* OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) W/5 fracture*)) AND.(View More ▼ | 9,527 document results | |
| 2 | TITLE-ABS-KEY((((step* OR stride*) W/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*)) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR "single support" OR "double support") W/2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*)) OR (((spatiotemporal OR "spatio-temporal") W/2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*)) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) W/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR rhythm* OR volume* OR bout* OR duration* OR distance* OR intensit* OR variabilit* OR asymmetr* OR symmetr* OR parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic* OR assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR measure* OR test*)))))) | 256,621 document results | |

TITLE-ABS-KEY(((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*)
W/3 obstruct*) OR copd OR parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans" OR ((multipl* OR
1 disseminated OR insular) W/3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat* OR ((hip*
OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR
subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) W/5 fracture*))

555,561 document results

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